

Original article

Antimalarial Prescription Patterns in a Health Insurance Clinic of a Tertiary Hospital in Bauchi, Northeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: In developing countries, malaria is a primary cause of morbidity and mortality and requires the correct use of antimalarial medications for effective management. The emergence of resistance and therapeutic failure to antimalarial medications has been linked to prescription practices for malaria. This study determined the prescribing patterns of antimalarial drugs at the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) clinic of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** The study was a descriptive, cross-sectional, retrospective study that investigated 1757 outpatient antimalarial prescriptions from ATBUTH's NHIA clinic during January to March 2022. Analysis was conducted using IBM® SPSS version 27 statistical packages. **Results:** About a quarter (25.9%) of all prescriptions contained antimalarial agents. Oral and injection routes accounted for 92.5% and 5.5% of antimalarial prescriptions, respectively, while 2% of prescriptions were for oral artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) following injections. Antimalaria drugs were combined with antibiotics in 39.8% of antimalaria prescriptions. Oral ACT and monotherapy were prescribed in 83% and 17% of cases, respectively. The most prescribed ACT was Artemether-Lumefantrine (80.2%), followed by Artesunate- Amodiaquine (2.1%), whereas the most prescribed oral monotherapy was Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (61.8%), while the commonest injectable monotherapy prescribed was artemether (61.8%). **Conclusion:** The antimalarial prescribing pattern in the clinic was largely in line with recommendations. However, injectable and monotherapy use is still common, posing a greater danger of undermining treatment policies. Antibiotic co-prescription with anti-malaria medications should be guarded, with additional interventions aimed at prescribers to improve anti-malarial drug use in Nigeria.

Keywords: Antimalaria, Artemisinin-based combination therapy, Health Insurance, Malaria, Prescriptions, Utilisation pattern.

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Introduction

Malaria, despite being preventable and curable, continues to be a significant illness of public health concern, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where it is a major cause of morbidity and mortality, remarkably affecting pregnant women and children who are more susceptible.¹ The World Health Organisation (WHO) asserts in its 2025 World Malaria Report that Africa constitutes 94% of the 282 million malaria cases and 95% of the global deaths recorded in 2024, with about 75% of the deaths occurring among children under five years.² Between 2015 and 2024, malaria cases increased by 18% while malaria deaths increased by 5.5%.²

Nigeria continues to have the highest malaria burden globally, contributing roughly 26% of all cases and about 30% of malaria-related deaths worldwide, including nearly 39% of deaths among children under five years.² Malaria also accounts for approximately 60% of outpatient visits to health facilities, 11% of maternal deaths and 30% of childhood mortality, with about a quarter of these deaths occurring mainly in infants under one year in Nigeria.³ In addition to the economic burden resulting from man-hour loss due to malaria infection, its accompanying sequelae, and the costs of treatment and control efforts, fatality rates from untreated and inadequately treated cases have been shown to be exceedingly high.⁴

Timely diagnosis and early treatment of malaria using effective, recommended anti-malarial medications is a major strategy in the disease control, according to malaria treatment guidelines, including those for Nigeria.^{3,5} In order to achieve effective therapeutic outcomes, healthcare workers need to practice in accordance with the treatment guidelines.³ Inappropriate prescriptions remain a significant worldwide problem, particularly in developing nations such as Nigeria.^{3,6} Rational drug use in the management of common and life-threatening tropical diseases such as malaria remains a significant challenge, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa.² Despite extensive control and eradication efforts over the past century, malaria remains a highly prevalent and devastating disease in tropical regions, largely due to inappropriate therapy and irrational drug use.⁶

Following WHO recommendations, Nigeria implemented a policy shift in 2005 to adopt ACT as both first- and second-line treatments for uncomplicated malaria. The treatment guidelines advocate the use of ACTs, with Artemether-lumefantrine (AL) identified as the drug of first choice.⁷⁻⁹ Evidence indicates that prescribing practices play a significant role in the emergence of antimalarial drug resistance. Thus, the effectiveness of new treatment policies depends largely on adherence to recommended guidelines by both healthcare providers and patients. Rational use of antimalarial drugs is crucial for ensuring treatment success and preventing the spread of resistant malaria parasites.¹⁰⁻¹² Inappropriate use of antimalarial medications in Nigeria has significant consequences for public health, including an increased risk of adverse drug reactions and the development of antimicrobial resistance, which may lead to treatment failure, poor clinical outcomes, and increased healthcare costs.³ Irrational use of antimalarial drugs constitutes a

major obstacle to effective malaria prevention and treatment. This challenge is largely driven by inappropriate prescribing practices that contribute to the emergence of resistance to antimalarial medications.¹² As a result, the success of treatment policies and guidelines depends substantially on adherence by healthcare providers and patients to recommended standards.

Advances in malaria control have largely been driven by two key strategies: the use of insecticides to target the *Anopheles* mosquito vector and the implementation of appropriate, effective antimalarial drugs for prompt, effective case management.¹³ Regrettably, numerous studies on malaria have indicated improper prescribing practices in healthcare facilities, attributed to prescribers' noncompliance with acceptable treatment guidelines.¹⁴ Studies in Nigeria have demonstrated notable deficiencies in rational drug use among healthcare professionals.^{13,15} Therefore, evaluating prescription patterns of antimalarial drugs can help identify both rational and irrational prescribing practices in malaria management. Therefore, the assessment of prescribing practices is an effective method for evaluating drug treatment policies and interventions. In 2022, the WHO formulated a strategy to mitigate antimalarial drug resistance in Africa and recommended consistent evaluation of antimalarial medication efficacy as being essential to guide treatment plans in malaria-endemic nations and to facilitate the prompt identification and response to drug resistance.¹¹

Both the WHO and the Nigerian National Malaria Control Programme recommend ACTs for confirmed cases of uncomplicated malaria. These guidelines are intended to ensure rational use of antimalarial agents, reduce the misuse of antimalarial drugs, and delay the emergence of resistance. Despite clear policy direction, challenges persist in translating guideline recommendations into consistent prescribing practices at the point of care.¹⁶ In spite of considerable efforts to eliminate or manage malaria, it remains the most widespread and fatal illness in the tropics, primarily due to inadequate treatment or illogical drug utilisation.¹⁶ The emergence of resistance and therapeutic failure to antimalarial medications has been linked to prescription practices for malaria because antimalarial medications must be used correctly for malaria to be managed effectively and to deter the spread of drug-resistant malaria.¹¹ The rise and proliferation of multidrug-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* are acknowledged as the foremost obstacles to malaria control, particularly in malaria-endemic nations. This resistance development is

greatly supported by irrational antimalarial prescriptions.¹¹ Rational antimalarial prescribing, in line with national and WHO treatment guidelines, is essential to ensure effective case management, prevent the emergence of drug resistance, optimise health outcomes, and promote efficient use of limited healthcare resources.¹⁷ Despite the availability of standard treatment guidelines, variations in antimalarial prescription practices persist across different levels of care and healthcare financing arrangements in Nigeria.³

The National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) was established to improve access to essential healthcare services and reduce out-of-pocket expenditure for enrollees¹⁸. It has significantly improved access to affordable healthcare services, particularly for individuals in the formal sector, where public servants are required to pay only about 10% of the cost of medications.¹⁹ A key objective of the scheme is to reduce the financial burden of healthcare on Nigerians by shifting healthcare financing from direct out-of-pocket payments to a more structured system of pooled funding.¹⁹ Because NHIA enrollees pay only a fraction of the cost of medications,²⁰ cost considerations and immediate drug affordability – factors known to strongly influence prescribing behaviour in fee-for-service or out-of-pocket payment settings – may exert less influence on prescription decisions within NHIA clinics. This unique financing context provides an important opportunity to examine antimalarial prescription patterns in a relatively cost-neutral environment.

Systematic evaluation of prescription patterns can therefore identify gaps between policy and practice, highlight areas of irrational drug use, and inform strategies to strengthen supply chain management and guideline implementation within NHIA settings. Although prior research has documented broader trends in prescribing patterns, there remains a need for up-to-date data on antimalarial prescribing practices in tertiary settings. One approach to addressing inappropriate malaria management practices is to promote research that generates relevant evidence on current treatment practices. Such information can help raise awareness, guide the allocation of necessary resources, and promote rational prescribing among healthcare providers, ultimately improving patient outcomes while minimising treatment costs.^{3,11} Assessing antimalarial drug use among insured patients attending a tertiary healthcare facility in this region is important for understanding providers' prescribing practices and for generating baseline evidence to inform the development of

appropriate interventions and policies to improve antimalarial drug use within the insurance scheme. Therefore, the primary objective of this study was to evaluate the prescribing pattern of anti-malaria in the NHIA clinic of ATBUTH Bauchi, Nigeria, in order to ascertain the adherence of prescribers to the National Antimalarial Treatment Guideline in the treatment of malaria infections, to make recommendations to improve rational antimalarial prescribing and ultimately patient care.

Materials and methods

Study setting and design: This was a descriptive, cross-sectional, retrospective study of outpatient prescriptions at the NHIA clinic of ATBUTH, Bauchi, Bauchi State, North-eastern Nigeria. ATBUTH is a tertiary health care facility with a capacity of over 700 beds. It serves as the teaching hospital for the College of Medicine of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University and is a participating Health Care Provider (HCP) on the NHIA. The prescriptions studied were generated by medical doctors, mainly in the NHIA clinic, and from various specialities on referrals. These patients access their NHIA-approved drugs with a 10% copayment only from the NHIA pharmacy unit.

Sample size: The WHO standards stipulate that a minimum of 600 encounters must be included in any study examining prescribing practices in healthcare institutions.²¹ Therefore, 1757 prescriptions within the study period were evaluated.

Inclusion criteria: Outpatient NHIA clinic prescriptions (encounters) that contained at least one prescribed drug for the period of January to March 2022.

Exclusion criteria: Prescriptions outside the study period, prescriptions for inpatients, duplicate prescriptions for the same patient encounter and non-drug prescriptions were excluded.

Data collection and analysis: Data were collected and recorded using a modified WHO prescriber indicator form²¹ based on the objective of this study, which consists of demographic information (age and sex), number of prescriptions with antimalaria, number of prescriptions with antibiotics, name of prescribed antimalaria drug, and route of administration of prescribed antimalaria. Data were fed directly into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 for analysis after cleansing. Results were presented using descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages.

Ethical issue: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics

Committee of the ATBUTH with approval number ATBUTH(REC) 0037/2021.

Results

A total of 1,757 prescriptions were analysed. There were more female encounters (56.5%) than males (43.5%). The highest proportion of patients (34.3%) was children aged 10 years and below, while the elderly (greater than 60 years) accounted for 1.3% (Table 1). Exactly 32.7% prescriptions had no age indicated.

Prevalence of antimalarial prescription

About a quarter (26.0%) of the total prescriptions contained antimalarial drugs, and antimalarial drugs were combined with antibiotics in 39.8% of antimalarial prescriptions. (Table 2)

Pattern of antimalarial prescription

Oral route accounted for 92.5%, while injection route accounted for 5.5% of antimalaria prescriptions; 2% of antimalaria prescriptions had oral ACT following monotherapy injections (Table 3). Injectable antimalarial drugs were present in 7.4% of antimalarial prescriptions, with the most commonly prescribed injectable monotherapy being artemether (61.8%) (Table 3).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of patients

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender (N=1757)	Male	764	43.5
	Female	993	56.5
	Total	1757	100
AGE	Indicated	1182	67.3
	Not indicated	575	32.7
	Total	1757	100
Age group (years) (N=1182)	≤ 10	406	34.3
	11-20	139	11.8
	21-30	214	18.1
	31-40	215	18.2
	41-50	133	11.2
	51-60	60	5.1
	>60	15	1.3
	Total	1182	100

Table 2: Prevalence of Antimalaria Prescription

Variables	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Antimalaria prescribed (N=1757)	457	26.0	1300	74.0
Antibiotics prescribed (N=1757)	848	48.3	909	51.7
Antimalaria or antibiotics Prescribed (N=1757)	1121	63.8	636	36.2
Antimalaria prescribed without antibiotics (457)	275	60.2	182	39.8
Antimalaria prescribed with antibiotics (n=457)	182	39.8	275	60.2
Antibiotics prescribed without antimalaria (n=848)	666	78.5	182	21.5

ACT was prescribed in 359 (83.1%) of oral antimalaria prescriptions, while monotherapy was prescribed in 73 (16.9%) of encounters. Artemether-Lumefantrine (AL) was the most prescribed ACT, accounting for 96.6% of all ACT prescriptions, followed by Artesunate-Amodiaquine (AA) (2.5%). Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and proguanil were the two oral antimalaria monotherapies prescribed, accounting for 90.4% and 9.6% of oral monotherapies, respectively (Table 3).

Discussion

The majority of the analysed prescriptions were for children under 10 years of age (34.3%) and for females (56.5%). This is similar to findings from a

previous study by Suleiman et al in Bayelsa, who found that the majority of those treated for malaria were females (55.7%) and children (68.0%).²² Another study in River state also reported 58.1% of antimalaria prescriptions for females, while 40.8% were for children less than 12years.¹² Ezeani et al. reported that 64.4% of antimalarial prescriptions were for females at a University insurance clinic in Awka.¹⁵ Our finding is also corroborated by the findings of studies conducted in Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria, where female patients and respondents aged 0-10years constituted the majority 57.3% and 55.5% respectively.²³ Okoro and Jamiu also reported that more than two-thirds (69.4%) of the prescriptions in the NHIS clinic of the

University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu, were written for female patients.²⁴

Table 3: Pattern of Antimalaria Prescription

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Route (457)	Oral only	423	92.5
	Injection only	25	5.5
	Oral + Injection	9	2.0
Antimalaria (457)	Yes	34	7.4
	No	423	92.6
Specific Injection (34)	Artemether	21	61.8
	ArteetherAB	11	32.3
	Artesunate	2	5.9
	Oral antimalaria (457)	Yes	432
Specific Oral antimalaria (432)	No	25	5.5
	Artemether + lumefantrine	347	80.3
	Artesunate + amodiaquine	9	2.1
	Artesunate + SP	1	0.2
	Dihydroartemisinin + piperazine	2	0.5
	Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine	66	15.3
	Proguanil	7	1.6

Joda and Ologunagba reported that 51% of NHIS prescriptions in Lagos were for female patients.²⁵ This shows that children and women constituted the largest proportion of the patients presenting to the outpatient clinic and depicts their vulnerability to malaria.⁶ The findings of our study, however, contradict those of Bruce et al in Awka, who found 55.1% of analysed prescriptions for males and 44.88% for females, with the age group 21-30years accounting for 55.9% of the prescriptions.²⁶ Builders et al. also found 21-50 years to be the most affected age group.²⁷ This difference may be explained by the fact that Bruce's study was conducted among University staff attending the University clinic, whereas ours was conducted among general health insurance patients.

Prevalence of antimalarial use: Antimalarial agents were present in 26% of prescriptions. This is similar to the finding in the NHIA clinic of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH), where 37.1% of prescriptions contained antimalarial medication.¹⁴ The prevalence of antimalaria prescription in our study is lower than 61% of

NHIA prescriptions reported in Lagos and 61.7% reported by Suleiman et al in Bayelsa.²² The differences observed in our findings compared to those from Lagos and Bayelsa may be attributable to our higher level of health facility (being a Teaching Hospital)

This study showed that the majority (83%) of malaria prescriptions were ACTs, which is consistent with studies conducted in Ghana and Cameroon.^{28,29} This finding is also consistent with the findings of other Nigerian studies. For example, Chukwuka et al found that ACT was prescribed for uncomplicated malaria treatment in 83.2% of cases.³⁰ Bagbi and Alagala reported that ACT was the most frequently prescribed antimalarial (12), and Arute et al reported a similar finding in Delta state, Nigeria.²³ Ango et al. reported a lower prevalence of ACT use (60.1%) and a higher prevalence of antimalarial monotherapy (39.9%) in outpatient prescriptions in Sokoto, Nigeria,⁶ which may be due to the study setting being a primary health care centre rather than a Teaching Hospital used in our study.

In 2005, Nigeria designated ACT as the preferred treatment for uncomplicated malaria, adhering to WHO recommendations⁷ and there has been a consistent rise in the utilisation of ACTs for treatment nationwide.³¹ This 83% ACT treatment for malaria in our study, however, fell short of the target of at least 90% effective treatment of malaria, i.e. ACT treatment according to the strategic plan.³² There was no use of artemisinin oral monotherapy in our study, probably because of its unavailability in the facility. This is commendable as the use of monotherapy is associated with resistance.¹¹ To address the challenge of multidrug-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum*, the WHO has recommended the use of combination therapies—particularly those containing artemisinin derivatives—which are currently the most effective treatments, given the documented resistance to many other antimalarial drugs.¹¹

There was strong adherence to the National treatment guideline at the study site. This pattern of antimalarial prescriptions in our study aligns with earlier findings that clinicians in tertiary institutions are more likely to comply with national recommendations.²⁷ Such adherence is essential, as proper acceptance and use of ACTs by healthcare professionals are critical for sustaining gains in malaria control. In contrast, the use of non-ACT regimens or monotherapy may increase the risk of treatment failure, promote drug resistance, and lead to higher rates of complications and mortality.¹¹

The most prescribed ACT was AL, which is in tandem with the findings of studies from Enugu (80.8%),²⁴ Awka (73.3%),²⁶ Delta (71.9%),³³ and PortHarcourt (71.1%)³⁴ all in Nigeria. Ayinbuomwan et al. reported that, amongst the ACTs, the most frequently used in Benin, Nigeria, was AL (77.4%), followed by dihydroartemisinin/piperazine (9.2%) and artesunate/mefloquine (3.6%), with the least preferred being artesunate/SP (2.2%).³⁵ Bagbi and Alagala reported that ACTs were the most frequently prescribed antimalarials, with AL at 73.1%, followed by Dihydroartemisinin/Piperazine and then Artesunate-Amodiaquine.¹² Also, 79.5% and 72.2% of AL prescriptions were reported from West African countries of Ghana and Cameroon, respectively,^{28,29} while 97.3% of ACT prescribed in Uganda was AL.³⁶

The use of AL as the most prescribed antimalarial in our study is consistent with the Nigerian National Antimalarial Policy, which designates AL as the first-line treatment for uncomplicated malaria.⁷ Our findings also agree with the recommendations of the WHO, which endorse ACTs such as artemether-lumefantrine, artesunate-amodiaquine, artesunate-mefloquine, dihydroartemisinin-piperazine, and artesunate-sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for the management of uncomplicated malaria.¹⁷ These agents are considered highly effective in both adults and children and currently form the backbone of malaria elimination strategies in most endemic regions, particularly in Africa, due to widespread resistance to older antimalarial drugs. Furthermore, they contribute to reducing mosquito infectivity, especially in settings with low to moderate malaria transmission.¹¹

The use of Artesunate-Amodiaquine (AA) in this study was limited to 2.5% of ACT, even though it was the alternative first-line drug in Nigeria. This is probably due to safety concerns, especially in adult patients.^{37,38} No single prescription of artemisinin-based oral monotherapy, although non-artemisinin-based monotherapy accounted for 16.9% of oral antimalaria prescriptions. The use of artemisinin-based monotherapy contradicts policy recommendations due to the risk of developing parasite resistance, largely attributable to its short half-life.³⁹ Although, the observed level of non-artemisinin monotherapy in this study indicates considerable inappropriate use of antimalarial drugs, it may partly be explained by the use of SP and proguanil for prophylaxis in pregnancy and children, respectively, in accordance with guidance from the WHO and the Nigerian National Antimalarial Treatment Policy, which recommends

SP for intermittent preventive therapy (IPT) in pregnancy due to its proven efficacy.⁹ This likely accounts for SP and proguanil being the only monotherapy regimens prescribed in this study. However, the study did not provide sufficient detail to accurately distinguish between appropriately prescribed prophylactic monotherapy and inappropriate use. A previous study similarly reported that SP is the most commonly prescribed antimalarial agent for malaria prevention in pregnant women.²⁷

In terms of antimalarial route, the oral route accounts for 92.5%, injections for 5.5%, and oral plus injections for 2% of antimalarial prescriptions. Injections were therefore prescribed in 7.4% of antimalarial prescriptions, which falls within the WHO acceptable limit of $\leq 20\%$. This is similar to 4.8% of prescriptions containing antimalaria injections in the NHIA clinic of UMTH Maiduguri.¹⁴ It is also similar to 8.69% and 5.89% reported by Bagbi and Alagala in two different health facilities in Rivers State.¹² Our finding is, however, in contrast to that of Afriyie et al., who reported an antimalaria injection rate of 33.6% in the Ghana Police hospital.²⁸ This higher injection compared to ours indicates a disproportionately high use of injectables in the management of malaria at the Hospital because the 6.9% of cases with complicated malaria who required injectable antimalarials for treatment cannot justify the 33.6% antimalaria injection used in that study.²⁸ Although our study did not classify the treated malaria, the low use of injections in the facility is commendable, as use of injectable medications is linked to a higher risk of adverse effects and increased healthcare costs.²⁴ The tendency to overprescribe injectable antimalarials is often driven by misconceptions among healthcare providers, as well as patients' belief that injections are more effective than other dosage forms.^{14,40} Injections are potent, fast-acting and useful formulations when clearly indicated. However, they are more expensive compared to other dosage formulations and require injection safety training. Additionally, the use of injections may elevate the risk of transmitting blood-borne infections, including viral hepatitis and HIV.⁴¹ In contrast, tablet formulations are generally the most prescribed because of their ease of administration. Antimalarial drugs in tablet form are typically well absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract.⁴² We found 39.8% of prescriptions containing both antimalarial and antibiotic agents. This finding is similar to 37.2% concomitant antibiotic prescription in the NHIA clinic in Enugu, reported by Okoro and Jamiu, 24, 31.2% reported by Ezeani et al. in the

University health clinic in Awka, Nigeria, 15, and 42.5% concomitant antibiotic use with antimalarial in a similar teaching hospital in Benin.¹³ Concomitant antibiotic prescription in our work is, however, lower than 49.1% and 62.5% reported in each of the two health facilities studied in River State, 12, and 48.5% reported by Bruce et al in Awka, Anambra State.²⁶ Nonetheless, the extent of concomitant antibiotic prescription of 39.8% in this study is great and is above the WHO-recommended range of <30%.⁴³ This signifies the over-prescription of antibiotics, which may result in antibiotic resistance and should consequently be discouraged. Overprescription of antibiotics will likely reduce the efficiency of malaria treatment and may lead to increased resistance in organisms exposed to such treatments.²³ Concomitant antibiotic prescription with antimalaria and vice versa is a common observation in developing nations. Our facility will therefore benefit from an antibiotic Stewardship program.

There is usually no recognised necessity for the co-prescription of antimalarial agents with antibiotics; such prescriptions typically address suspected co-infections, suggesting the prescriber's uncertainty about the correct diagnosis or an intent to preempt undetected infections. The excessive use of antibiotics may lead to the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, as well as increased adverse effects and healthcare costs.¹⁵ Therefore, this finding underscores the urgent need for enhanced identification of nonmalaria fever and urges physicians to use antibiotics judiciously to mitigate adverse health effects.

The high concomitant antibiotic prescription can also be explained by the proportion of children (34.3%) in the study population. Age was found to be a predictor of the co-prescription of antimalarial drugs with antibiotics in a previous study.²⁴ Children were more prone to receiving coprescriptions of antimalarial medications and antibiotics compared to adults in developing nations.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ Some of the proposed reasons are that children are at elevated risk of recurrent infections in other systems, including the respiratory and gastrointestinal systems.¹² Concomitant drug prescriptions contribute to irrational use of antimalarial drugs and elevated health care costs. Consequences of co-medication with antibiotics include polypharmacy, poor adherence, drug interactions, adverse drug reactions and treatment failures, as well as antibiotic resistance.⁴⁷

A high rate of presumptive malaria diagnosis is frequently observed among healthcare professionals, especially in high-transmission

settings, where there is a tendency to assume that malaria-related fevers can be readily distinguished from other causes of fever.¹³ However, clinical diagnosis alone has low specificity and often leads to over-treatment, resulting in inefficient use of limited resources and further burdening an already fragile healthcare system.¹³ This practice may also encourage inappropriate co-prescription of antibiotics, as noted in this study (39.8%), thereby increasing selective pressure for the development and spread of antibiotic-resistant organisms. To mitigate this challenge, the WHO recommends parasitological confirmation to accurately identify malaria cases and support the rational use of antimalarial drugs.¹¹ Ultimately, the effectiveness of WHO or national antimalarial treatment policies in any country depends largely on how well both healthcare providers and patients adhere to recommended treatment guidelines.^{28,48}

Limitations

The limitations of our study include the retrospective collection of data from pharmacy outpatient prescriptions. This caused an unrealistic collection of parasitology and clinical profiles of patients. Hence, it is difficult to establish the ratio of cases that were tested and confirmed before treatment. Consequently, the extent of overdiagnosis and resultant over-treatment for malaria could not be appropriately determined. An earlier study supported this assumption.²² Therefore, the use of the drug could not be linked with the clinical decisions that informed the prescriptions. For example, since the type of malaria being treated was not examined, it is also difficult to determine whether antimalarial drug regimens prescribed were appropriate for the type of malaria diagnosed at the hospital. Prescriptions from the antenatal clinic were not excluded, which likely affected antimalarial prescription patterns due to the use of SP for Intermittent Preventive Therapy (IPT) in pregnancy. Due to the time lag between data collection and the publication of the findings, the results may not reflect current antimalarial drug prescribing practices in the study setting.

Conclusion

The antimalarial prescribing pattern in the NHIA clinic was satisfactory and aligned with current National and WHO guidelines for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria, with most prescriptions being ACTs. The proportion of antimalarial prescriptions in injectable form falls within the WHO-acceptable limit of ≤20%. However, there remains a sizeable number of health workers who

engage in the prescription of monotherapy for malaria treatment. Also, the frequency of co-prescribing antibiotics with antimalarial drugs was high.

Recommendations

- Laboratory tests to confirm or exclude bacterial infections prior to the co-prescription of antibiotics with ACT.
- The prescription guideline should further be adhered to.
- A more extensive study that encompasses secondary, tertiary, and private hospitals to ascertain the prescribing practices for malaria therapy across various levels of care within the state.
- Organization of training and retraining of prescribers on evidence based rational drug decision and further adherence to antimalaria prescription guidelines.
- More analytical investigations to determine the suitability of malaria diagnosis alongside prescribed antimalarial medications and dosage protocols.
- Efforts to reduce inappropriate therapy, and antibiotics use to avoid the development of resistance to ACT, while simultaneously improving the administration of ACT for malaria treatment.

Conflict of Interest: Authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' Contribution: All authors have substantial contribution to the work.

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